

Safe load out process with safe ballasting and safe Mooring of barges at ports for Heavy and long structures by using Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT)¹

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Abstract

In the Marine industry, there are numerous complex and high-risk activities pertaining to construction and port operations. These activities pose imminent danger to man, machine and environment if not exerted with various safety management systems, machinery related safety protocols, environmental considerations and process related safety systems.

Carrying out of Load out process for complex and heavy machinery, equipment, material and construction related heavy and critical components are essential and sometimes it may lead to devastating and catastrophic incidents if not considered the preconditions and process safety.

In the marine construction industry, Load-Out of drilling platforms, heavy machinery and equipment, bridge components and segmental parts are crucial. For this comprehensive technical and innovative safety systems needs to be developed and exerted into the process to ensure safe loading process is ensured with the help of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT), Barges, loading beam and towers, ballasting / de-ballasting requirements while will enable the system to function in a way that lead the entire process into the easier and safer manner.

Keywords

Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT), Ballasting / De- ballasting, fenders, Mooring, Load out.

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INTRODUCTION

Load out process especially when it is complex and super heavy machinery / equipment loading are posing imminent risk considering various parameters like, barge capacity, type of barge used, Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) and its operation, barge anchoring patterns, ballasting / De-ballasting is not considered for machine and workplace safety while initiating load out processes.

It has been evidenced that many incidents recorded during the load out process of heavy and complex machinery loading on to the barges from land. The incidents recorded including capsizing barges due to inadequate ballasting and de-ballasting sequential process, unsafe and unauthorized operation of Self-Propelled Modular Transporters (SPMT), lack of coordination and communication gap between the crew, inadequate or unsafe anchoring patterns of the barge and environmental challenges like rough sea, inclement weather condition etc.

Advance preparation of Load out process as given in the below fig.01.

Fig.01: Advance preparation sequence for load out

1. Common works prior to Load-out:

1.1 Sequence:

The load out operation will be executed by using Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) method. Load out to be performed in 2(two) phases.

Phase 1 is moving from construction location to the quay side.

Phase 2 moves from the quay side to final position on the barge.

- Remove any obstacle on the Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) route. Clear all metal pieces, sharp objects on the way which may harm the Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT)tires.
- Remove and clear any obstacles on the barge deck which can obstruct the load out. (include control room at the front of barge, if necessary)
- The speed of the loading and progress of the ballast will be coordinated within each stage.
- The load out speed should be maximum 90m/Hr. During the load out the level of the barge shall be monitored visually and by monitoring system.

1.2. Load Out Sequence:

Load out process sequence as given in the below fig.2 is to be followed to avoid the bypassing of the crucial steps and important activities which can lead to delay and incidents.

Fig.2: Load out sequence

2. Installation of Link plates:

Link plate is installed so that Self Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) can easily cross between the quay wall and the barge and is used to transfer the axle load of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter to the quay wall and barge.

Link plate to be positioned accurately between the quay wall and the barge. Link plates thickness should be according to the load bearing capacity of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) and Load carried by SPMT during the load-out process.

3. Installation of Fenders:

Fender should be installed in advance at the quay wall for the following purposes of use. The compressive force of the barge by the mooring force is transferred to the quay wall. Fenders are used for absorbing the kinetic energy of a boat or vessel berthing against quay wall or another vessel.

The regular space between the quay wall and the barge are kept in the load out. Fenders are used to prevent damage to boats, vessels and berthing structure.

4. Safe Load Out Procedure: for the safe load out, below are the stage wise elaboration to be ensured:

4.1 Load Out procedure stage wise:

Stage-1: Barge standby:

Step 1-1: Mooring line installation to be done to secure the barge from accidentally moving out of the alignment due to waves and tidal variations.

Step 1-2: Lifting Tower Installation on the barge to lift the intended material which is planned for load out process.

Step 1-3: Lifting box installation to facilitate the bottom support for the load

Step 1-4: Lifting Jack installation to facilitate the safe lifting of the intended load.

Stage-2: Load Out Preparation:

Step 2-1: Setting of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) in place and direction and alignment for load out process to avoid directional issues.

Step 2-2: Link plate to be installed between Barge and Berthing face for safe movement of SPMT from land to Barge by carrying the load.

Step 2-3: Stern side lifting box setting (Outside)

Step 2-4: Barge control with the help of mooring ropes tied and stabilization of Barge for Load Out process initiation.

Stage-3: Load Out:

Step 3-1: Process the Load out activity with the help of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) from land portion to Barge deck

Step 3-2: Stern side lifting box setting (Inside)

Stage -4: Large Girder Jack-up:

Step 4-1: Installation of lifting jack wire ropes

Step 4-2: Jack-up the large block slowly and steady

Step 4-3: Ensure evacuation of Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) in reverse direction from the barge top to land portion.

Stage-5: Sea Fastening process:

Step 5-1: Put down the large block on barge deck which was lifted to facilitate the Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) move out of the barge deck.

Step 5-2: Sea Fastening

Stage -6: Departure:

Step 6-1: Uninstall the mooring provisions from land to barge

Step 6-2: Remove the link plate installed for the connectivity between Barge to Land portion at berthing face.

Step 6-3: Use the Tugboats to push / pull the barge and sail out as per intended directions.

Sequential process step wise explained in the Fig.3 below:

Fig.3 Sequential Safe Load out process with 100meter Barge.

5. Mooring winch:

A barge will be moored to the quay on the stern side by steel wires and winch system during load-out operation. Mooring winches will be located on the transportation barge and connected to the quay wall bits.

After load-out, the mooring winches will be used for the Barge anchoring at installation site; the status is as follows below in Table-1 Mooring Winch description.

Description	Specification	Remarks
Capacity	15ton	
Quantity	8 set	
Winding speed	5~15 meters per Minutes	
Holding Capacity	50 ton	
Winch wire rope	6 x 37 IWRC 35 milli meter	IWRC=Independent Wire rope core
Power source	AC 440V, 60Hz, 3Ph	AC=Alternative Current V=Colts Hz=Hertz Ph= Phase

Table-1: Mooring winch description

Mooring of the barge should be done to secure the barges from moving uncontrollably leading to untoward incidents. These Mooring plans are required to ensure the stabilization and security of the barges, Safety of the crew and other personnel on vessels, operational efficiency and risk mitigation and compliance purposes.

Mooring plan as given in the Fig.4 as below: to secure the barges / vessels.

Fig.4: Mooring plan of Barge for Load out process

5.1 Weather Criteria:

Weather criteria considerations to be ensured as given below in the table-2

Subject	Value
Wind Speed	12m/s(=23.3knots)
Current Speed	3knots
Average significant wave height	0.5meters
Wave peak period	10.0seconds

Table-2: Weather criteria

5.2 Windage Projection Area above Barge Deck:

Wind projection or wind speed projected with force against the barge is as given in the below in table3

Subject	Projection Area (m2)
Side View	258.8
Front View	1600.9

Table-3: Windage project area:

1.3 Rising Tide:

The incoming rising sea level low and high levels are to be considered as given in the Table -4 as below:

Condition	Current direction (Degree)	Wind direction (degree)	Wave direction (degree)	Max. Tension (ton)	Max. Tension (ton)	Percent Strength	Safety Factor	Result
A	180	0	180	8-D	13.8	15%	2.0	O. K
B	180	45	180	8-D	19.2	21%	2.0	O. K
C	180	90	180	8-D	26.9	29%	2.0	O. K
D	180	135	180	8-D	34.2	37%	2.0	O. K
E	180	180	180	8-D	39.1	43%	2.0	O. K
F	180	225	180	8-D	35.8	39%	2.0	O. K
G	180	270	180	8-D	26.1	28%	2.0	O. K
H	180	315	180	8-D	16.4	18%	2.0	O. K

Table-4: Rising tide

Note: D= Density

5.3 Falling Tide:

Condition	Current direction (degree)	Wind direction (degree)	Wave direction (degree)	Max. Tension Line	Max. Tension (ton)	Percent Strength	Safety Factor	Result
A	0	0	0	4-C	39.1	43%	2.0	O. K
B	0	45	0	4-C	34.2	37%	2.0	O. K
C	0	90	0	4-C	26.9	29%	2.0	O. K
D	0	135	0	4-C	19.2	21%	2.0	O. K
E	0	180	0	4-C	13.8	15%	2.0	O. K

F	0	225	0	4-C	16.4	18%	2.0	O. K
G	0	270	0	4-C	26.0	28%	2.0	O. K
H	0	315	0	4-C	35.8	39%	2.0	O. K

Table-5: Falling Tide

Note: C= Sublunar Point.

6 Ballasting Plan:

- The ballasting will be controlled by barge operating manager with engineer who prepared ballasting calculation report.
- Prior to the load out, all ballast tanks should be inspected by project manager to secure the barge during the load out.
- During the load out, the barge tanks shall be ballasted or de-ballasted to their required quantities as indicated in the ballast calculation report.
- The barge will be ballasted/de-ballasted until the required draft, heel and trim have been achieved before proceeding to the next stage.

6.1: Level Control during Load Out process:

- Level target will be used for monitoring bare trim and heeling.
- Level targets are installed to measure the level of FWD and AFT on both sides of the barge.
- To measure the level, Theodolite should be installed on the left and right of the quay wall.
- Load out manager should monitor the measured value continuously and control the barge according to the measured value.

Fig-5: Target level control plan of Barge during ballasting

7 Ballasting Control Process:

- To ensure proper monitoring of the ballast water transferring between tanks, one experienced person will be assigned to supervise the ballast operation, the sounding value, barge level at each step etc.
- This person will strictly monitor the pumps that he was assigned and control these pumps if necessary. He should also advise ballast engineer immediately of any mal functioning such as sudden loss of pressure or other concern.
- It is extremely important to confirm the working condition of ballast pumps and ballasting operation.
- Walkie-talkies will be used on private channels to control ballast pumps.
- The communication from the controllers is systematic. Requestor reply must be in the order of tank number to avoid confusion. Supervising works should focus on 2 notices.
- The barge will be checked all time, the barge check includes trimming check and heeling check, one responsible worker checks the ullage of the barge both side port and starboard each end of the barge.
- The result of measurement has to be sent to ballast supervisor by, walkie-talkie each 5 minute for treatment, maximum trimming allowable is 300mm and maximum heeling allowable is 100mm.
- Pumping duration must be counted by stopwatch. Pump capacity is shown by manufacturer & defined by pumping in tanks.

8 Roles & Responsibilities:

Roles and Responsibility of the team involved in the activity according to the work scope load out operation given in Table-06

Designation	Responsibilities
Load out manager:	Action as the Master of load out operation, load out manager will be responsible for Command the load out operation- manage all load out activities- Co-ordinate with all parties for load out successfully.
Safety manager:	Safety Manager acts as the leader of HSE and fully responsible to oversee and advise the HSE aspects of entire project- Supervise HSE during load out operation- make sure all load out activities are compliance with HSE regulation of project.
Engineering manager:	Be responsible for technical of whole project.
Operation manager:	Supervise load out operation- Co-ordinate with all other staffs during load out operation.
Ballast manager:	Acts as the master of barge and ballasting, he will be fully responsible for be responsible for barge and ballast activities- Supervise and manage the ballasting operation.

SPMT manager:	Acts as the master of SPMT operation, he will be fully responsible for be responsible for SPMT operation. supervise and manage the SPMT operation. SPMT operator will operate SPMT.
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Table: 06 Roles and responsibilities of individual for the activity.

Conclusion / Recommendation:

Load out process is very critical when handling the heavy and long objects thus it is required the extra care to complete the process by using innovative and technical solutions considering environmental conditions, quay conditions, Sea conditions and the design drawings along with technical data of the objects. The load out process requires, Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT) for smooth shifting processes, considerations to be made for mooring patterns, Ballasting calculations, winch calculations and safety requirements to be exerted for the safe completion of complex activities like Load Out processes.

References:

1. **Marliana, W., Salma, S. A., & Hakim, B. P.** (2024). Work accident risk control in road construction projects with the HIRADC approach. *Jurnal Indonesia Sosial Teknologi*, 5(7), 3290–3304. <https://doi.org/10.59141/jist.v5i7.1149>
2. **Prastowo, T. Y., Imsarif, R. L. M., Sanjaya, D., & Taryana, N.** (2024). Risk analysis of occupational safety and health (K3) using the HIRADC method on chiller replacement works: A case study. *Civilla: Jurnal Teknik Sipil Universitas Islam Lamongan*, 9(2), 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.30736/cvl.v9i2.1266>
3. **Wijaya, R.** (2024). Risk analysis in concrete structure work using the HIRADC method on the Hermina Ciawi Hospital project. *Calamity: A Journal of Disaster Technology and Engineering*, 1(2), 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.61511/calamity.v1i2.2024.338>
4. **Setiawan, L., Rahmatullah, A., Muhammad, I., Rini, A. S., Hanan, S., & Pratama, T. R. H.** (2023). Penerapan K3 menggunakan HIRARC (hazard identification, risk assessment and risk control) pada perusahaan konstruksi di Cilegon. *Industrika: Jurnal Ilmiah Teknik Industri*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.37090/indstrk.v8i2.1516>
5. **Sari, Y. A., Baskara, I. W. Y., Riana, I. N., & Ariana, K. A.** (2022). Analisis keselamatan dan kesehatan kerja menggunakan metode hazard identification and risk assessment pada proyek konstruksi. *Reinforcement Review in Civil Engineering Studies and Management*, 1(2), 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.38043/reinforcement.v1i2.4105>
6. **Indah Suci Rahayu.** (2022). BIM-integrated construction safety risk assessment at the design stage of building projects. *Jurnal KaLIBRASI: Karya Lintas Ilmu Bidang Rekayasa Arsitektur, Sipil, Industri*, 5(2), 124–131. <https://doi.org/10.37721/kalibrasi.v5i2.112>
7. **Pratama, A. Z. W., Wardana, H., Mulia, & Ritonga, D. A.** (2025). Hazard analysis and risk control in industrial building construction work: A review article. *TEKNOSAINS: Jurnal Sains, Teknologi dan Informatika*, 12(2), 338–344. <https://doi.org/10.37373/tekno.v12i2.1598>

8. **Pramesthi, S. A., Anwar, R., & Susanti, L.** (2025). Risk analysis of occupational safety and health analysis using the HIRARC method at building construction. *ASTONJADRO*, 14(2), 484–497. <https://doi.org/10.32832/astonjadro.v14i2.17359>
9. **Gibbs, M. T.** (2015). Risk assessment and risk management: A primer for marine scientists. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 72(3), 992–996. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsu232>
10. **Mousavi, M., Ghazi, I., & Omarae, B.** (2017). Risk assessment in the maritime industry. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 7(1), 1377–1381. <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.836>
11. **Tao, J., Liu, Z., Wang, X., Cao, Y., Zhang, M., Loughney, S., Wang, J., & Yang, Z.** (2024). Hazard identification and risk analysis of maritime autonomous surface ships: A systematic review and future directions. *Ocean Engineering*, 307, 118174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2024.118174>
12. **Zhao, X., Wen, Y., Zhang, F., Han, H., & Huang, Y.** (2023). A review on risk assessment methods for maritime transport. *Ocean Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.114577>.
13. **Li, H., Zhou, Q., & Wang, Y.** (2023). Maritime risk assessment using a non-linear spatial multi-criteria decision method: A case study in the Bohai Sea and Yellow Sea, China. *Ocean Engineering*, 288, 115994. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.115994>
14. **ander, L., Eisen, E. A., Stentz, T. L., Spanjer, K. J., Wendland, B. E., & Perry, M. J.** (2011). *Near-miss reporting system as an occupational injury preventive intervention in manufacturing*. *American Journal of Industrial Medicine*, 54(1), 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajim.20904>
15. **Shen, X., & Marks, E.** (2016). *Near-miss information visualization tool in BIM for construction safety*. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 142(4), 04015100. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001100](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001100)
16. **inarsson, S., & Brynjarsson, B.** (2008). Improving human factors, incident and accident reporting and safety management systems in the Seveso industry. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 21(5), 550–554. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2008.05.004>
17. **Belenky, V. L.** (1993). A capsizing probability computation method. *Journal of Ship Research*, 37(3), 200–207.
18. **Chang, C.-H., Kontovas, C. A., Yu, Q., & Yang, Z.** (2020). Risk assessment of the operations of maritime autonomous surface ships. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 207, Article 107–114.
19. **Alyami, H., Lee, P. T. W., Yang, Z., Ramin, R., Bonsall, S., & Wang, J.** (2014). An advanced risk analysis approach for container port safety evaluation. *Maritime Policy & Management*, 41(5), 434–450. (DOI not provided here; available in databases.)
20. **Khatsuriya, J. R., & Gaur, A.** (2025). Perceived effectiveness of near-miss reporting on proactive safety performance in construction: A mixed-methods study from India. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Health*, 15(3), 209–221. <https://doi.org/10.3126/ijosh.v15i3.80888>
21. **Basso, B., Carpegna, C., Dibitonto, C., Gaido, G., Robotto, A., & Zonato, C.** (2004). Reviewing the safety management system by incident investigation and performance indicators. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 17(3), 225–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2004.02.004>

22. Cambraia, F. B., Saurin, T. A., & Formoso, C. T. (2010). Identification, analysis and dissemination of information on near misses: A case study in the construction industry. *Safety Science*, 48(1), 91–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2009.06.006>
23. Bird, F. E., & Germain, G. L. (1996). *Loss control management: Practical loss control leadership* (Rev. ed.). International Loss Control Institute. (ISBN 9780880610544;)
24. van der Schaaf, T. W. (1992). *Near-miss reporting in the chemical process industry* (PhD thesis). Technische Universiteit Eindhoven. <https://doi.org/10.6100/IR384344>
25. *Safety and/or hazard near miss reporting in an international energy company*. (n.d.).
26. Drever, F., Hughes, H., Osborn, S., Williams, S., & Shaw, R. (n.d.). *Adverse events and near-miss reporting in the NHS*.
27. Guedes Soares, C., & Teixeira, A. P. (2001). Risk assessment in maritime transportation.
28. Borrelli, M., Smith, T. L., & Mague, S. T. (2021). Vessel-based, shallow water mapping with a phase-measuring sidescan sonar.
29. Thomas Telford Ltd. (2005). *Construction health and safety in coastal and maritime engineering*. Thomas Telford Publishing. (Book;)
30. *Vessel safety guide: Guidance for offshore renewable energy developers*. (2015). (Technical guide;)
31. Wellner, R. F. (n.d.). *Orthotropic steel decks for highway bridges*. Bethlehem Steel Corporation. (Technical paper;)
32. Cruickshank, I., & Cork, S. (2005). *Construction health and safety in coastal and maritime engineering* (Technical Report). Thomas Telford Publishing. ISBN 978-0727733450
33. World Meteorological Organization. (1999). *Metoccean services for marine pollution emergency response operations (MARPOLSER 98): Proceedings* (WMO/TD-No. 959 & 960). World Meteorological Organization.
34. RenewableUK. (2015). *Vessel safety guide: Guidance for offshore renewable energy developers*. RenewableUK. <http://www.renewableuk.com/en/publications/index.cfm/vessel-safety-guide>
35. Chakrabarti, S. K. (Ed.). (2005). *Handbook of offshore engineering* (2 vols.). Elsevier Science. <https://www.elsevier.com/books/handbook-of-offshore-engineering/chakrabarti/978-0-08-044381-2>
36. Dudás, K., Dunai, L., & Kövesdi, B. (2015). *Assessment of fatigue behaviour of orthotropic steel bridge decks using monitoring system*. In *Proceedings of the 6th Fatigue Design Conference (Fatigue Design 2015)* (Abstract FD15-113).
37. Volpi Ghirardini, A., Losso, C., Libralato, G., Zanella, M., Keppel, E., Sigovini, M., & Tagliapietra, D. (2010). *Sea water piling: Traditional or alternative materials? An integrated biological and ecotoxicological evaluation in Venice Lagoon (Italy)*. In *Proceedings of the 39th CIESM Congress* (Vol. 39, p. 697). International Commission for the Scientific Exploration of the Mediterranean Sea.
38. Volpi Ghirardini, A., Losso, C., Libralato, G., Zanella, M., Keppel, E., Sigovini, M., & Tagliapietra, D. (2010). *Sea water piling: Traditional or alternative materials? An integrated*

biological and ecotoxicological evaluation in Venice Lagoon (Italy). In Proceedings of the 39th CIESM Congress (Vol. 39, p. 697). International Commission for the Scientific Exploration of the Mediterranean Sea.

- 39. Gudmestad, O. T. (2002). Risk assessment tools for use during fabrication of offshore structures and in marine operations projects. *Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering*, 124(3), 153–161. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1492825>**

